

A Appendices

Table 1. Publication Venues of Static Analysis-Driven APR Studies

No	Venue Name	Venue Type	No. of Studies
1	Foundations of Software Engineering (FSE)	Conference	6
2	International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)	Conference	4
3	ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology	Journal	4
4	IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution (ICSME)	Conference	2
5	International Conference on Verification, Model Checking, and Abstract Interpretation	Conference	2
6	Symmetry	Journal	2
7	ACM Asia Conference on Computer and Communications Security	Conference	1
8	Automated Software Engineering	Journal	1
9	Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems (ASPLOS)	Conference	1
10	Empirical Software Engineering	Journal	1
11	Generative programming and component engineering	Conference	1
12	IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing	Journal	1
13	Automated Software Engineering (ASE)	Conference	1
14	IEEE International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering	Conference	1
15	Journal of Systems and Software	Journal	1
16	IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering	Journal	1
17	International Conference on Engineering of Complex Computer Systems (ICECCS)	Conference	1
18	International Conference on AI Foundation Models and Software Engineering (Forge)	Conference	1
19	International Conference on Informatics (ICI)	Conference	1
20	International Conference on Machine Learning	Conference	1
21	International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)	Journal	1
22	International Conference on Blockchain and Trustworthy Systems	Conference	1
23	International Symposium on Research in Attacks, Intrusions and Defenses	Conference	1
24	International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE)	Conference	1
25	Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages	Journal	1
26	Source Code Analysis and Manipulation (SCAM)	Conference	1
27	Symposium on Applied Computing	Conference	1
28	USENIX Security Symposium	Conference	1
29	USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation	Conference	1
30	IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Automated Program Repair (APR)	Workshop	1

Table 2. Static Analysis-Driven APR Tools: Associated SA Tools, Targeted Defect Types, and Programming Languages

APR Tool	SA Tool(s)	Defect Type(s)	Language(s)
SymlogRepair [25]	Digger, Securify2, Yang et al.'s rules [41]	NPEs, Vulnerabilities	Java, Python, Solidity
InferFix [19]	Infer	NPEs, RM, Concurrency	Java, C#
Hippodrome [8]	RacerD	Concurrency	Java
EffFix [44]	Pulse	NPEs, RM	C
Phoenix [3]	FindBugs	Bugs, Vulnerabilities, CS	Java
Crayons [9]	EBA	Concurrency, API Usage	C
RLFixer [35]	Infer, PMD, CF, Codeguru, Spotbugs	RM	Java
Getafix [2]	Infer, Error Prone	NPEs, API Usage, Semantic	Java
SAVER [16]	Infer	RM	C
GFix [26]	GCatch	Concurrency	Golang
BovInspector [15]	Fortify	Vulnerabilities	C
Seader [45]	Seader	Vulnerabilities	Java
AIFix4SecCode [22]	SpotBugs, SonarQube, PMD	Vulnerabilities	Java
ACR [23]	Coverity	Vulnerabilities	C
Sorald [12]	SonarQube	Bugs, Vulnerabilities, CS	Java
SDRacer [37]	Clang Tool 3.4	Concurrency	C
EagleRepair [31]	ReSharper, SonarQube	Bugs, Vulnerabilities, CS	C#
VFIX [13]	Securify, Slither, Smartcheck	Vulnerabilities	Solidity
Two Timin' [17]	Slither	Vulnerabilities	Solidity
SAPFIX [30]	Infer	NPEs	Java
OptimalFix [20]	Smartcheck, Mythril, Slither	Vulnerabilities	Solidity
STYLER [27]	Checkstyle	CS	Java
DTSFix [11]	DTSJava	NPEs, Semantic, Control Flow	Java
PyTy [7]	Pyre Type Checker	Semantic	Python
SpongeBugs [29]	SonarQube, SpotBugs	API Usage, Syntax, Control Flow	Java
Abtahi and Azim [1]	SonarQube	Bugs, Vulnerabilities, CS	JavaScript, Python, Java, Docker
CORE [36]	CodeQL, SonarQube	Bugs, Vulnerabilities, CS	Java, Python
IFIX [38]	D4 framework	Concurrency	Java
RelFix [24]	Relda2	RM	Dalvik bytecode
TFix [4]	ESLint	Syntax, Semantic, Control Flow, Method Invocation, API Usage, RM, Concurrency, CS	Javascript
SmartFix [34]	VeriSmart	Vulnerabilities	Solidity
EVMPATCH [32]	Securify, Osiris, teEther	Vulnerabilities	Solidity
Elysium [14]	Osiris, Oyente, Mythril	Vulnerabilities	EVM bytecode
Weimer [39]	FindBugs, WN	NPEs, RM, Concurrency, API Usage, Vulnerabilities, Control Flow	Java
TIPS [6]	Slither, Mythril	Vulnerabilities	Solidity
AutoFix [40]	Saber	RM	C
Shahab et al. [33]	KIUWAN	Vulnerabilities	C++
DTSFix [10]	DTS	NPEs, Semantic, RM, Control Flow	Java
CFix [18]	AFix	Concurrency	C, C++
CDRep [28]	CRYPTOLINT	Vulnerabilities	Java
GPURepair [21]	GPUVerify	Concurrency	CUDA, OpenCL
LLOR [5]	LLOV	Concurrency	C, C++, Fortran
SCRepair [42]	Slither, Oyente	Vulnerabilities	Solidity

Defect Types: NPEs = Null Pointer Exceptions, RM = Resource Management, CS = Code Smells

Table 3. Static Analysis-Driven APR Tools: Repair, Validation, and False Alarm Mitigation Techniques

APR Tool	Repair Technique				Validation Technique					SA False Alarms Removal Methods								
	CB	LB	HB	PB	SA	TS	LB	DV	EV	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
SymlogRepair [25]	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y
InferFix [19]	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y
Hippodrome [8]	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	
EffFix [44]	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
Phoenix [3]	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
Crayons [9]	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
RLFixer [35]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
Getafix [2]	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
SAVER [16]	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
GFix [26]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
BovInspector [15]	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	
Seader [45]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
AIFix4SecCode [22]	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
ACR [23]	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
Sorald [12]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
SDRacer [37]	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	
EagleRepair [31]	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
VFIX [13]	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	
Two Timin' [17]	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	
SAPFIX [30]	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
OptimalFix [20]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
STYLER [27]	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
DTSFix [11]	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
PyTy [7]	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
SpongeBugs [29]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	
Abtahi and Azim [1]	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
CORE [36]	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
IFIX [38]	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
RelFix [24]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
TFix [4]	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
SmartFix [34]	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
EVMPATCH [32]	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	
Elysium [14]	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
Weimer [39]	C	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
TIPS [6]	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
AutoFix [40]	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
Shahab et al. [33]	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
DTSFix [10]	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	
CFix [18]	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
CDRep [28]	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
GPURepair [21]	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
LLOR [5]	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
SCRepair [42]	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	

Repair Techniques: CB = Constraint Based, LB = Learning Based, HB = Heuristic Based, PB = Pattern Based

Validation Techniques: SA = Static Analysis, TS = Test Suite, LB = Learning Based, DV = Dynamic Validation, EV = External Validation Only

SA False Alarms Removal Methods: A = Graph Theory, B = Model Checking, C = Data Fusion, D = Machine Learning, E = Mathematical & Statistical Models, F = Alert Type Selection: G = Dynamic Detection, H = Contextual information, I = None

Table 4. Static Analysis-Driven APR Tools: Evaluated Benchmarks and Performance

APR Tool	Benchmark(s)	Language(s)	# Successful Repairs	Patch Correctness
SymlogRepair [25]	NPE10	Java	100%	80%
	PL11	Python	91%	55%
	SC63	Solidity	100%	98%
InferFix [19]	InferredBugs	Java	N/A	76%
		C#	N/A	65%
Hippodrome [8]	JaConTeBe, Tomcat, Guava	Java	67%	67%
EffFix [44]	SAVER, OpenSSL, Linux kernel	C	83%	61%
Phoenix [3]	Open Source Projects	Java	85%	80%
Crayons [9]	Linux Kernel	C	85%	85%
RLFixer [35]	NJR-1	Java	66%	95%
Getafix [2]	Open Source Projects	Java	30%	42%
SAVER [16]	Open Source Projects	C	74%	99%
GFix [26]	Open Source Projects	Golang	83%	100%
BovInspector [15]	Open Source Projects	C	100%	100%
Seader [45]	Open Source Projects	Java	N/A	99%
AlFix4SecCode [22]	Open Source Projects	Java	70%	N/A
ACR [23]	SVCOMP	C	52%	100%
Sorald [12]	Open Source Projects	Java	65%	100%
SDRacer [37]	Open Source Projects	C	100%	100%
EagleRepair [31]	Open Source Projects	C#	64%	97%
VFIX [13]	Etherscan, SolidiFI	Solidity	94%	94%
Two Timin' [17]	Etherscan	Solidity	98%	100%
SAPFIX [30]	Open Source Projects	Java	79%	48%
OptimalFix [20]	SmartBugscurated, JiuZhou [43], SolidityFi	Solidity	86%	92%
STYLER [27]	Open Source Projects	Java	41%	N/A
DTSFix [11]	Open Source Projects	Java	82%	N/A
PyTy [7]	PyTyDefects	Python	85%	54%
SpongeBugs [29]	Open Source Projects	Java	85%	84%
Abtahi and Azim [1]	EIS dataset from Team Eagle	JavaScript, Python, Java, Docker	94%	98%
CORE [36]	SQJava	Java	77%	N/A
	CQPy, CQPyUS	Python	83%	52%
IFIX [38]	Open Source Projects	Java	100%	100%
RelFix [24]	Open Source Projects	Dalvik bytecode	N/A	100%
TFix [4]	Open Source Projects	Javascript	68%	49%
SmartFix [34]	IO, EL-SU, RE, TX Bench	Solidity	81%	97%
EVMPATCH [32]	Real-world Ethereum smart contracts	Solidity	100%	96%
Elysium [14]	Horus	EVM bytecode	100%	96%
Weimer [39]	Open Source Projects	Java	43%	N/A
TIPS [6]	SmartBugscurated, ContractDefects	Solidity	88%	88%
AutoFix [40]	SPEC2000, Open Source Projects	C	100%	N/A
Shahab et al. [33]	Open Source Projects	C++	37%	N/A
DTSFix [10]	Open Source Projects	Java	58%	76%
CFix [18]	Open Source Projects	C, C++	98%	98%
CDRep [28]	Google Play, SlideMe	Java	95%	87%
GPURepair [21]	OpenCL Kernels	OpenCL	48%	N/A
	CUDA Kernels	CUDA	48%	N/A
LLOR [5]	Parallel Benchmark Collection	C, C++	79%	79%
		Fortran	50%	50%
SCRepair [42]	Etherscan Vulnerable Dataset (EV-DS)	Solidity	44%	81%

N/A = Not Reported

References

- [1] Seyed Moein Abtahi and Akramul Azim. 2025. Augmenting Large Language Models with Static Code Analysis for Automated Code Quality Improvements. In *2025 IEEE/ACM Second International Conference on AI Foundation Models and Software Engineering (Forge)*. 82–92. doi:10.1109/Forge66646.2025.00017
- [2] Johannes Bader, Andrew Scott, Michael Pradel, and Satish Chandra. 2019. Getafix: learning to fix bugs automatically. *Proc. ACM Program. Lang.* 3, OOPSLA, Article 159 (Oct. 2019), 27 pages. doi:10.1145/3360585
- [3] Rohan Bavishi, Hiroaki Yoshida, and Mukul R. Prasad. 2019. Phoenix: automated data-driven synthesis of repairs for static analysis violations. In *Proceedings of the 2019 27th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (Tallinn, Estonia) (ESEC/FSE 2019)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 613–624. doi:10.1145/3338906.3338952
- [4] Berkay Berabi, Jingxuan He, Veselin Raychev, and Martin Vechev. 2021. TFix: Learning to Fix Coding Errors with a Text-to-Text Transformer. In *Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Machine Learning (Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, Vol. 139)*, Marina Meila and Tong Zhang (Eds.). PMLR, 780–791. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v139/berabi21a.html>
- [5] Utpal Bora, Saurabh Joshi, Gautam Muduganti, and Ramakrishna Upadrasta. 2025. LLOR: Automated Repair of OpenMP Programs. In *Verification, Model Checking, and Abstract Interpretation*, Krishna Shankaranarayanan, Sriram Shankaranarayanan, and Ashutosh Trivedi (Eds.). Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 121–136.
- [6] Qianguo Chen, Teng Zhou, Kui Liu, Li Li, Chunpeng Ge, Zhe Liu, Jacques Klein, and Tegawendé F Bissyandé. 2023. Tips: towards automating patch suggestion for vulnerable smart contracts. *Automated Software Engineering* 30, 2 (Sept. 2023), 31.
- [7] Yiu Wai Chow, Luca Di Grazia, and Michael Pradel. 2024. PyTy: Repairing Static Type Errors in Python. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/ACM 46th International Conference on Software Engineering (Lisbon, Portugal) (ICSE '24)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 87, 13 pages. doi:10.1145/3597503.3639184
- [8] Andreea Costea, Abhishek Tiwari, Sigmund Chianasta, Kishore R, Abhik Roychoudhury, and Ilya Sergey. 2023. Hippodrome: Data Race Repair Using Static Analysis Summaries. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* 32, 2, Article 41 (March 2023), 33 pages. doi:10.1145/3546942
- [9] Juan Cruz-Carlon, Mahsa Varshosaz, Claire Le Goues, and Andrzej Wasowski. 2023. Patching Locking Bugs Statically with Crayons. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* 32, 3, Article 56 (April 2023), 28 pages. doi:10.1145/3548684
- [10] Yukun Dong, Mengying Wu, Shanchen Pang, Li Zhang, Wenjing Yin, Meng Wu, and Haojie Li. 2020. Automated Program-Semantic Defect Repair and False-Positive Elimination without Side Effects. *Symmetry* 12, 12 (2020). doi:10.3390/sym12122076
- [11] Yukun Dong, Li Zhang, Shanchen Pang, Wenjing Yin, Mengying Wu, Meng Wu, and Haojie Li. 2020. Automatic Repair of Semantic Defects Using Restraint Mechanisms. *Symmetry* 12, 9 (2020). doi:10.3390/sym12091563
- [12] Khashayar Etemadi, Nicolas Harrant, Simon Larsén, Haris Adzemovic, Henry Luong Phu, Ashutosh Verma, Fernanda Madeiral, Douglas Wikström, and Martin Monperrus. 2023. Sorald: Automatic Patch Suggestions for SonarQube Static Analysis Violations. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing* 20, 4 (2023), 2794–2810. doi:10.1109/TDSC.2022.3167316
- [13] Pengcheng Fang, Peng Gao, Yun Peng, Qingzhao Zhang, Tao Xie, Dawn Song, Prateek Mittal, Sanjeev Kulkarni, Zhuotao Liu, and Xusheng Xiao. 2024. VFIX: Facilitating Software Maintenance of Smart Contracts via Automatically Fixing Vulnerabilities. In *2024 IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution (ICSME)*. 13–24. doi:10.1109/ICSME58944.2024.00013
- [14] Christof Ferreira Torres, Hugo Jonker, and Radu State. 2022. Elysium: Context-Aware Bytecode-Level Patching to Automatically Heal Vulnerable Smart Contracts. In *Proceedings of the 25th International Symposium on Research in Attacks, Intrusions and Defenses (Limassol, Cyprus) (RAID '22)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 115–128. doi:10.1145/3545948.3545975
- [15] Fengjuan Gao, Linzhang Wang, and Xuandong Li. 2016. BovInspector: automatic inspection and repair of buffer overflow vulnerabilities. In *Proceedings of the 31st IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (Singapore, Singapore) (ASE '16)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 786–791. doi:10.1145/2970276.2970282
- [16] Seongjoon Hong, Junhee Lee, Jeongsoo Lee, and Hakjoo Oh. 2020. SAVER: scalable, precise, and safe memory-error repair. In *Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE 42nd International Conference on Software Engineering (Seoul, South Korea) (ICSE '20)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 271–283. doi:10.1145/3377811.3380323
- [17] Abhinav Jain, Ehan Masud, Michelle Han, Rohan Dhillon, Sumukh Rao, Arya Joshi, Salar Cheema, and Saurav Kumar. 2023. Two Timin': Repairing Smart Contracts With A Two-Layered Approach. In *2023 Second International Conference on Informatics (ICI)*. 1–6. doi:10.1109/ICI60088.2023.10421047
- [18] Guoliang Jin, Wei Zhang, and Dongdong Deng. 2012. Automated Concurrency-Bug Fixing. In *10th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI 12)*. USENIX Association, Hollywood, CA, 221–236. <https://www.usenix.org/conference/osdi12/technical-sessions/presentation/jin>
- [19] Matthew Jin, Syed Shahriar, Michele Tufano, Xin Shi, Shuai Lu, Neel Sundaresan, and Alexey Svyatkovskiy. 2023. InferFix: End-to-End Program Repair with LLMs. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM Joint European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (San Francisco, CA, USA) (ESEC/FSE 2023)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1646–1656. doi:10.1145/3611643.3613892
- [20] Ningkang Jing, Shanshan Chen, and Kunhang Bao. 2025. OptimalFix: An Automated Framework for Fixing Vulnerabilities in Smart Contracts Effectively. In *Blockchain, Metaverse and Trustworthy Systems*, Debiao He, Jiajing Wu, Chen Wang, and Huawei Huang (Eds.). Springer Nature Singapore, Singapore, 61–74.
- [21] Saurabh Joshi and Gautam Muduganti. 2021. GPURepair: Automated Repair of GPU Kernels. In *Verification, Model Checking, and Abstract Interpretation*, Fritz Henglein, Sharon Shoham, and Yakir Vizel (Eds.). Springer International Publishing, Cham, 401–414.
- [22] Judit Jász, Péter Hegedűs, Ákos Milánkovich, and Rudolf Ferenc. 2022. An End-to-End Framework for Repairing Potentially Vulnerable Source Code. In *2022 IEEE 22nd International Working Conference on Source Code Analysis and Manipulation (SCAM)*. 242–247. doi:10.1109/SCAM55253.2022.00034
- [23] William Klieber, Ruben Martins, Ryan Steele, Matt Churilla, Mike McCall, and David Svoboda. 2021. Automated Code Repair to Ensure Spatial Memory Safety. In *2021 IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Automated Program Repair (APR)*. 23–30. doi:10.1109/APR52552.2021.00013
- [24] Jierui Liu, Tianyong Wu, Jun Yan, and Jian Zhang. 2016. Fixing Resource Leaks in Android Apps with Light-Weight Static Analysis and Low-Overhead Instrumentation. In *2016 IEEE 27th International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE)*. 342–352. doi:10.1109/ISSRE.2016.15
- [25] Yu Liu, Sergey Mechtaev, Pavle Subotić, and Abhik Roychoudhury. 2023. Program Repair Guided by Datalog-Defined Static Analysis. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM Joint European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (San Francisco, CA, USA) (ESEC/FSE 2023)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1216–1228. doi:10.1145/3611643.3616363
- [26] Ziheng Liu, Shuofei Zhu, Boqin Qin, Hao Chen, and Linhai Song. 2021. Automatically detecting and fixing concurrency bugs in go software systems. In *Proceedings of the 26th ACM International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems (Virtual, USA) (ASPLOS '21)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 616–629. doi:10.1145/3445814.3446756
- [27] Benjamin Lorient, Fernanda Madeiral, and Martin Monperrus. 2022. Styler: learning formatting conventions to repair Checkstyle violations. *Empirical Software Engineering* 27, 6 (Aug. 2022), 149.
- [28] Siqi Ma, David Lo, Teng Li, and Robert H. Deng. 2016. CDRep: Automatic Repair of Cryptographic Misuses in Android Applications. In *Proceedings of the 11th ACM on Asia Conference on Computer and Communications Security (Xi'an, China) (ASIA CCS '16)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 711–722. doi:10.1145/2897845.2897896

- [29] Diego Marcilio, Carlo A. Furia, Rodrigo Bonifácio, and Gustavo Pinto. 2020. SpongeBugs: Automatically generating fix suggestions in response to static code analysis warnings. *Journal of Systems and Software* 168 (2020), 110671. doi:10.1016/j.jss.2020.110671
- [30] Alexandru Marginean, Johannes Bader, Satish Chandra, Mark Harman, Yue Jia, Ke Mao, Alexander Mols, and Andrew Scott. 2019. SapFix: Automated End-to-End Repair at Scale. In *2019 IEEE/ACM 41st International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering in Practice (ICSE-SEIP)*. 269–278. doi:10.1109/ICSE-SEIP.2019.00039
- [31] Martin Odermatt, Diego Marcilio, and Carlo A. Furia. 2022. Static Analysis Warnings and Automatic Fixing: A Replication for C# Projects. In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering (SANER)*. 805–816. doi:10.1109/SANER53432.2022.00098
- [32] Michael Rodler, Wenting Li, Ghassan O. Karame, and Lucas Davi. 2021. EVMPatch: Timely and Automated Patching of Ethereum Smart Contracts. In *30th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 21)*. USENIX Association, 1289–1306. <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity21/presentation/rodler>
- [33] Aamir Shahab, Muhammad Nadeem, Mamdouh Alenezi, and Raja Asif. 2020-08-01. An automated approach to fix buffer overflows. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (Online)* 10, 4 (2020-08-01).
- [34] Sunbeom So and Hakjoo Oh. 2023. SmartFix: Fixing Vulnerable Smart Contracts by Accelerating Generate-and-Verify Repair using Statistical Models. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM Joint European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (San Francisco, CA, USA) (ESEC/FSE 2023)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 185–197. doi:10.1145/3611643.3616341
- [35] Akshay Utture and Jens Palsberg. 2023. From Leaks to Fixes: Automated Repairs for Resource Leak Warnings. In *Proceedings of the 31st ACM Joint European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (San Francisco, CA, USA) (ESEC/FSE 2023)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 159–171. doi:10.1145/3611643.3616267
- [36] Nalin Wadhwa, Jui Pradhan, Atharv Sonwane, Surya Prakash Sahu, Nagarajan Natarajan, Aditya Kanade, Suresh Parthasarathy, and Sriram Rajamani. 2024. CORE: Resolving Code Quality Issues using LLMs. *Proc. ACM Softw. Eng.* 1, FSE, Article 36 (July 2024), 23 pages. doi:10.1145/3643762
- [37] Yu Wang, Fengjuan Gao, Linzhang Wang, Tingting Yu, Jianhua Zhao, and Xuandong Li. 2022. Automatic Detection, Validation, and Repair of Race Conditions in Interrupt-Driven Embedded Software. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 48, 1 (2022), 346–363. doi:10.1109/TSE.2020.2989171
- [38] Zan Wang, Haichi Wang, Shuang Liu, Jun Sun, Haoyu Wang, and Junjie Chen. 2020. IFIX: Fixing Concurrency Bugs While They Are Introduced. In *2020 25th International Conference on Engineering of Complex Computer Systems (ICECCS)*. 155–164. doi:10.1109/ICECCS51672.2020.00025
- [39] Westley Weimer. 2006. Patches as better bug reports. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Generative Programming and Component Engineering (Portland, Oregon, USA) (GPCE '06)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 181–190. doi:10.1145/1173706.1173734
- [40] Hua Yan, Yulei Sui, Shiping Chen, and Jingling Xue. 2016. Automated memory leak fixing on value-flow slices for C programs. In *Proceedings of the 31st Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing (Pisa, Italy) (SAC '16)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1386–1393. doi:10.1145/2851613.2851773
- [41] Chenyang Yang, Rachel A Brower-Sinning, Grace Lewis, and Christian Kästner. 2023. Data Leakage in Notebooks: Static Detection and Better Processes. In *Proceedings of the 37th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (Rochester, MI, USA) (ASE '22)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 30, 12 pages. doi:10.1145/3551349.3556918
- [42] Xiao Liang Yu, Omar Al-Bataineh, David Lo, and Abhik Roychoudhury. 2020. Smart Contract Repair. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* 29, 4, Article 27 (Sept. 2020), 32 pages. doi:10.1145/3402450
- [43] Pengcheng Zhang, Feng Xiao, and Xiapu Luo. 2020. A Framework and DataSet for Bugs in Ethereum Smart Contracts. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution (ICSME)*. 139–150. doi:10.1109/ICSME46990.2020.00023
- [44] Yuntong Zhang, Andreea Costea, Ridwan Shariffdeen, Davin McCall, and Abhik Roychoudhury. 2025. EffFix: Efficient and Effective Repair of Pointer Manipulating Programs. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* 34, 3, Article 69 (Feb. 2025), 27 pages. doi:10.1145/3705310
- [45] Ying Zhang, Ya Xiao, Md Mahir Asef Kabir, Danfeng (Daphne) Yao, and Na Meng. 2022. Example-based vulnerability detection and repair in Java code. In *Proceedings of the 30th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Program Comprehension (Virtual Event) (ICPC '22)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 190–201. doi:10.1145/3524610.3527895